

ISic0647

I.Sicily inscription 0647

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 311

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][τὸ]ν κόσμον ἅπαντα ε
2. [---][βασιλ]έως καὶ βασιλίδος
3. [---][ἀμέμ]πτως καὶ ἀκαταγνώ
4. [στω]ς ἔζησαν μοι ἔτη ἰδ' ἓν
5. [---]αυτῶν ἔτη κη ὀρκί
6. [ζωτὸν]παντοκράτορα καὶ
7. [τὸν]ἐπιμέλ[λον]τα αἰῶνα
8. [---]εν ἀνῦξαι
9. [---][ἐκεῖ]νων κατ[ά]
10. [θεσιν ---]

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644889

PHI 316288

PHI 332935

PHI 332936

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité*. 106: 79-118. At 88-89 no.6 fig.9

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